

Living Music: The Future of Listening and Composing

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ABSTRACT

This talk covers my project to consolidate an ongoing movement in music under the concept of Living Music. Living Music is an inclusive category for interactive, generative, co-created, and all other types of non-linear or boundless audio works. Most importantly, a piece of Living Music has an element of autonomy beyond the listener, as determined by the composer.

My presentation will explore the compositional potential this affords artists, as well as how Living Music can bring new ways of listening that can change our relationship to music altogether.

1. INTRODUCTION

All music before recording technology was Live Music, performed locally and never exactly the same twice. Recorded Music brought about the capture and mass repeatability of a single performance for mass distribution, and now digital distribution provides perfect, infinite playback of a single piece of music, where anyone can hear the exact same piece of music at any time.

Living Music exists between Recorded Music and Live Music: it is music created with elements of ephemerality, interactivity or externalities built into the composition that change the music according to the composer's intention. A piece of Living Music is never the same twice, offering a bespoke listening experience for the audience while using existing venues of digital music streaming for greater accessibility.

2. LIVING MUSIC

Living Music harnesses digital tools like Web Audio to offer a unique method of composing and consuming music.

This is not a new idea, but the current conditions are right to consolidate this method of creating and consuming music into a cohesive movement in music. This a unique way of creating and consuming music that has existed for a long time, since concepts of randomness, generative systems and aleatory were first incorporated into musical composition.

However, the current approach is fractured, with many pieces defined and sorted by the technique used to create them, like one-off album-apps, micro-sites, generative systems, site-specific works, bespoke plugins or discrete online apps. Living Music can

act as a broad banner, joining many pieces and techniques under a common mission: creating music with autonomy from the listener.

There is a confluence of creativity and technological opportunity that offers musicians and developers a chance to broaden the reach of their work and build a community of creators and listeners who are asking more from the music they consume.

But in order to be heard, we need to meet our listeners where they already are. While no popular existing music platform currently hosts this kind of living content, widely-used existing platforms (Spotify, Apple Music, YouTube Music, Bandcamp) can all play a crucial role in this movement. These platforms offer an opportunity to discover artists creating Living Music, followed by an invitation to discover with the full experience of the living piece on another platform, as the artist originally intended.

To illustrate this more fully, we can use the following metaphor:

A piece of Living Music is like a sculpture in a park: to visit it in person is the full experience. When you visit it in person it is different based on ephemeral conditions (time, weather, etc) and you as an observer have agency (explore it from all angles, visit at different times, etc) that prevents you from sharing the exact experience of the sculpture with any other observer.

Whereas recorded music is like a photograph of the sculpture: a single, unchanging snapshot of the piece with a specific set of conditions from a single angle and a limited field of view that can be perfectly shared by all.

Streaming platforms are the the most primed to distribute Living Music, but currently they are primarily being used solely for playback of pre-recorded audio files or broadcast of live performance streams with limited interactivity or living elements.

By consolidating the kind of music we're creating under the label of Living Music, we can offers listeners a cohesive category to engage with and follow, where a listener can know that there's going to be an extra element to the music that makes it all the more unique and worth giving their full attention.

3. WEB AUDIO AND LIVING MUSIC

Web Audio will be a foundational tool for creating and distributing Living Music, and it can play several roles, explored below.

Web Audio as a sole generator: all sounds are created and controlled by the Web Audio. This is the case for many generative music projects using Web Audio, where the user can listen to a unique and non-repeating performance each time they access the piece. The listener can render snippets of the pieces to download (like a photograph of a sculpture that you took yourself).

Web Audio as an instrument: Living Music with pre-recorded elements can be created and distributed with Web Audio providing a living element / instrument in the composition. For example, a pre-recorded file is hosted online, and a new bespoke instrument / part is rendered in web audio and mixed into the pre-recorded parts to create a new bespoke version. This approach offers a simpler, more collaborative method for traditional musicians to experiment with adding living elements to their traditionally composed and recorded music.

Web Audio as arranger: Web Audio can also be used to uniquely arrange pre-recorded samples into new compositions on demand, creating bespoke combinations and completely new arrangements for each listener, each time.

4. FVELD: A LIVING MUSIC LABEL

fveld is a music label dedicated to building a community of developers, artists and listeners around Living Music. Our first release, Living Drone, represents one of the simplest executions of a piece of Living Music: random recombination of pre-recorded music.

Living Drone is about using a concept to build a bridge between the past, present and future with contiguous music. It is a collaborative work that is released as editions, gathered and published in its final medium as a constant streaming playlist. Each piece begins and ends with the same drone sound, and it played on shuffle with crossfading enabled, connecting disparate pieces from artists between editions and offering a unique performance of the piece each time it is played.

5. IN DEVELOPMENT

There are several more pieces in development at the moment to further explore the possibilities of Living Music, outlined below:

Tone Rooms: A tool that generates ambient works of music based off of the precise dimensions of a room / space. Each piece relates to a specific room, using compatible tones based on the resonant frequencies of your space, optimised for the natural amplification the room dimensions naturally cause.

The initial release will be from rooms in my own home (entryway, living room, bathroom, studio, kitchen, bedroom, shed) and the Therefore, the ideal venue for each of these pieces will be the room for which it was created. Listeners can then use the same generative tool (built in partnership with Alex Bainter) to generate their own bespoke pieces by inputting the room dimension for each of their own rooms and creating new files.

Music for Home Automation: Sound design for everyday life, this piece is a series of 24 sounds and musical movements created to mark time and give shape to the macro rhythms of daily life. Created with a suite IFTTT automations, the sounds are triggered at specific intervals to create a long-term classical conditioning environment for the listener. Over time, the musicians release new versions of the sounds and evolve their composition in real time.

Common Tragedies: a piece of Living Music that each time it is streamed, the music degrades in complexity and quality for all listeners, permanently. Over time, the piece is consumed fully for all listeners, revealing additional elements of the composition (patterns, melodies) as it decays while highlighting the externalities of digital consumption. Additional movements can be released over time, also starting in full complexity and resolution, only to be consumed over time as the preceding movements were.

6. ABOUT

baern (they) is the living music project of non-binary sound artist & composer Brian Barth. Based in Amsterdam, baern's work revolves around composition for audience co-creation, interactivity, digital aleatory and living music. They are the founder of fveld, a music label dedicated to living music; releasing interactive, generative, location-based, and all other types of non-linear or boundless works.